

AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS ON MARKETING OF ANANDA DAIRY (GHEE) IN VARANASI DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH

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Abstract:

The present study entitled "An Economic Analysis on Marketing of Ananda Dairy (Ghee) in Varanasi District of Uttar Pradesh". It was founded that there are two marketing channels involved in marketing of Ananda Dairy (Ghee) in Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh, (Channel 1 – Producer-Wholesaler-Consumer), (Channel 2- Producer-Wholesaler- Retailer-Consumer). The majorly preferred marketing channel by respondents in the study area is Channel 2. In channel 1, total marketing cost is Rs.48, total marketing margin is Rs 206, marketing efficiency of channel 1 is 2.20% and Producer's Share in Consumer Rupees in channel 1 is 81.42%. In channel 2, total marketing cost is Rs.63, total marketing margin in channel 2 is Rs.197, marketing efficiency of channel 2 is 2.17% and Producer's share in Consumer rupees in channel 2 is 80.70%.

Keyword:, Marketing Efficiency, Marketing Margin, Marketing Cost, Producer's Share.

Introduction

Ghee is a type of clarified butter that originated in ancient India and has been used in Indian cuisine for centuries. It is made by heating butter until the water content evaporates, and the milk solids separate and settle at the bottom. The remaining golden liquid is ghee. Ghee has a distinct nutty aroma and a rich, buttery flavor. It has a higher smoke point compared to regular butter, which means it can be heated to higher temperatures without burning. This makes ghee an excellent cooking fat for sautéing, frying, and deep-frying. One of the key advantages of ghee is its long shelf life. Due to the removal of milk solids, ghee has a much lower moisture content than butter, making it less prone to spoilage. It can be stored at room temperature for several months without refrigeration. Ghee is also highly regarded for its potential health benefits. It is rich in fat-soluble vitamins such as A, D, E, and K and contains conjugated linoleic acid (CLA), which may have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Ghee is lactose-free and often tolerated by individuals with lactose intolerance. However, it is still high in saturated fats and should be consumed in moderation. In addition to culinary uses, ghee has traditional applications in Ayurvedic medicine and is used for massage, moisturizing the skin, and even in religious ceremonies. Ananda Ghee is a popular brand of ghee in India. Ananda, a dairy company based in India, produces and sells Ananda Ghee as part of its product line. Ananda Ghee is made from pure cow's milk butter and undergoes the process of clarification to remove impurities and moisture, resulting in a smooth and golden ghee. Ananda Ghee is known for its high quality and authentic taste. It has a rich, nutty flavor and a creamy texture that adds a distinctive touch to various Indian dishes. Ananda Ghee has a high smoke point, making it suitable for deep frying, sautéing, and baking. Like other ghee products, Ananda Ghee has a longer shelf life compared to regular butter due to the removal of milk solids. It can be stored at room temperature without refrigeration for

an extended period. Ananda Ghee is widely used in Indian cuisine and is an essential ingredient in many traditional recipes. It is valued not only for its flavor and versatility but also for its potential health benefits. Ghee is believed to have Ayurvedic properties and is considered beneficial for digestion, strengthening the immune system, and nourishing the body. Overall, ghee is a versatile and flavorful ingredient that adds depth and richness to a wide range of dishes while offering potential health benefits.

Research Methodology:**Selection of the District:**

There are 75 District and 18 division in Uttar Pradesh state. Out of these Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh was selected for the present study on the basis of maximum area under cattle rearing and milk production.

Selection of Block:

There are 7 block in the district. Out of these Kashi Vidyapeeth was selected purposively for the study.

Selection of Villages:

A complete list of all villages of Kashi Vidyapeeth block was obtained from the block development office. Thereafter these villages was arranged in ascending order on the basis of area of cattle rearing and milk production. Thus, out of total villages 5% villages was selected randomly for the present study.

Selection of Respondents:

From the selected village, list of all the cattle rearing farmer and milk producer was obtained from the block development office in each selected village. Ascending order on the basis of size of their land holding for the selection of cultivators from families was listed and 10% farmers from each village were randomly selected and then the selected farmers were classified into five sizes of groups.

Table 1: Selection of Respondents:

District	Block	Villages	Respondents				Total	
			Marginal	Small	Semi-medium	Medium		Large
Varanasi	Kashi Vidyapeeth	Bakhani	6	5	5	2	1	19
		Balirampur	7	5	5	4	2	23
		Bandepur	3	5	6	5	1	20
		Chhitawni Kot	7	5	3	6	1	22
		Dafalpur	5	6	4	5	1	21
		Daudapur	5	3	2	4	1	15
TOTAL			33	29	25	26	7	120

Analytical Tools

Mean Marketing Efficiency

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

(Net price received by producer's – Consumer price)
Total marketing cost

Marketing Cost:

Table 2: Marketing Efficiency , Marketing Margin, Marketing Cost and Producer's Share in Consumer Rupee of Ananda Dairy (Ghee) in Channel 1

Channel 1: Producer -Wholesaler-Consumer.

$$\text{Marketing Cost (MC)} = \frac{\Delta TC}{\Delta Q}$$

Producer's Share in Consumer Rupees:
(Consumer price paid price /Net price received by producer)x100

Marketing Margin

Marketing Margin= Producer price – Raw material

Results And Discussion

Sr. No	Particulars	Value in Rupees/kg
		Ghee
		Rs
1.	Producer sale price to wholesaler	504
Cost incurred by the producer		
i	Packing cost	10
ii	Packing material cost	10
iii	Transportation cost	5
iv	Market cost	3
v	Labour cost	6
vi	Loading and Unloading cost	4
vii	Miscellaneous charges	10
Total cost (i-vii)		48
viii	Margin of Producer	150
ix	Net price received by producer	456
2	Wholesaler sale price to Consumer	560
i.	Margin of Wholesaler	56
A	Total Marketing cost	48
B	Total Market margin	206
C	Marketing Efficiency	2.20%
D	Producer Share in Consumer Rupees	81.42%

Table 2: Reveals the marketing price of the Ananda dairy Ghee channel -I , supplied by the producer was Rs.504 and the net price received by producer of Ananda dairy Ghee Rs.456 . Meanwhile, the cost incurred by Ananda dairy Ghee producer in marketing is Rs.48 and Rs.150, as profit per kg of Ananda dairy Ghee . Simultaneously, the wholesaler purchased Ananda dairy Ghee from the producer as Rs.504/kg. with Rs.56, as profit, by which the final

selling price of Ananda dairy Ghee was Rs.560/kg . Finally, the selling price of Ananda dairy Ghee to the consumers was Rs.560/kg, Rs Eventually, the Marketing Efficiency of Ananda dairy Ghee was seen to be 2.20%.3 per kg, the total marketing cost was Rs.48, ; the producer's share in Consumer rupee of Ananda dairy Ghee is 81.42%.

Table 3: Marketing Efficiency , Marketing Margin, Marketing Cost and Producer's Share in Consumer Rupee of Ananda Dairy (Ghee) in Channel 2

Channel 2: Producer- Wholesaler-Retailer- Consumer.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value in Rupees
		Ghee
		Rs.
1	Sale price of producer to wholesaler	504
A	Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler	48
B	Margin of Producer	150
2	Sales price of Wholesaler to Retailer	544
A.	Cost incurred by the Wholesaler	
I	Loading & Unloading charges	2
II	Carriage up to shop	2
III	Weighting charges	3
IV	Town charges	3
V	Transportation	3
VI	Losses & Miscellaneous charges	2

Total Cost (i-vi)		15
VII	Margin of wholesaler	25.20
3	Margin of Village Merchant/Retailer	21.70
4	Consumers paid price	565
A	Total marketing cost	63
B	Total marketing margins	197
C	Marketing Efficiency	2.17%
D	Producer's Share in Consumer rupees	80.70%

Table 3 : It has been revealed that the marketing price of the Ananda dairy Ghee supplied by the wholesaler was Rs. 544, the cost of marketing incurred by the Ananda dairy Ghee wholesaler is Rs.15 and the net price received by the producer the Ananda dairy Ghee 1 kg is Rs.-456. the profit margin of the Ananda dairy Ghee wholesaler Rs.25.20. finally the selling price of the Ananda dairy Ghee from retailer to consumer is Rs.565 and the profit margin of retailer of O the Ananda dairy Ghee is Rs 21.70 and thus the final price of the Ananda dairy Ghee is Rs.565 . Eventually, the Marketing Efficiency of the Ananda dairy Ghee was seen to be 2.17%, the total marketing cost was Rs.63, and total market margin in channel 2 is Rs.197 , the producers share in consumer rupees the Ananda dairy Ghee and milk through channel 2 is 80.70%.

Conclusion:

From the survey conducted it is observed that Ananda dairy has good distribution channel in the market. From the study it is observed that factors which make its distribution channel effective are on time delivery, quality products, no damage to products, fast and effective supply chain. It is also observed during the study that the majority of the customers are satisfied with the Ananda dairy products because of its good quality reputation. Some customers are not satisfied with the Ananda dairy products because not easily available product in the market, less supply chain management scheme. Ananda dairy is a dairy great potential. Its huge base of membership, good net worth and support and support from government makes it a strong unit. However increasing complexities of the market and absence of pace can make a welfare unit. Efficient and dynamic management with strong leadership innovative strategies and proactive decision making can help Ananda dairy to improve its performance in the market.

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